

DIF: Bayes Factors

Differential Item Functioning: Comparison of Traditional and Modern Bayesian Methods

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The nuisance effects of differential item functioning (DIF) obstruct valid inferences. These undesirable effects occur when equal-ability examinees from different groups differ in their probability of answering an item correctly. Because ability estimates derive from a model that assumes DIF is not present, any inaccuracy of this assumption promotes inappropriate inferences, and therefore, testing programs (or researchers) are responsible for ensuring no group is disadvantaged. Typically, this responsibility translates into the procedure of discovery and resolution, first subjecting items to a DIF analysis and then addressing flagged items by either reviewing, removing, or rewriting them. DIF analysis, then, is pivotal to test, assessment, and measurement integrity.

Most common analyses flag items by relying on methods that quantify evidence for DIF. An alternative but related perspective is to provide evidence that DIF does *not* exist. Often times this perspective goes undiscussed in the DIF literature (cf. Holland & Wainer, 1993). This is because some of the most popular methods of discovering DIF rely on frequentist/deterministic approaches. Here, researchers take a null model that, in some form or fashion, characterize a dataset as DIF-free and use it to determine how extreme their observed data are when modeled with DIF. When the data are so extreme that they are unlikely to come from the null DIF-free model, they reject the null as being the true model. Researchers state the evidence of extremeness with the conventional p-value—the probability of the data given the null model. When the data are *not* extreme, they fail to reject the null model. This is a desirable outcome (i.e., the item is DIF-free), but paradoxically, researchers cannot provide evidence for the null. Instead, they can only provide (lack of) evidence for the alternative DIF model. Frequentist/deterministic approaches cannot provide evidence that DIF is not present (i.e., the null).

Although they cannot provide evidence for the null, frequentist approaches remain quite useful for detecting effects of various kinds. Whether used for detecting DIF or any other confirmatory or experimental research, the frequentist approach is robust and powerful under certain conditions. One essential condition is that sample sizes must be sufficiently large so that asymptotic sampling theories hold. When this condition is met (as is often the case with the typical sample sizes in psychometrics), frequentist tests are often the most powerful kind. For this reason, it remains a popular statistical analysis among researchers.

Recently, researchers have explored the use of latent class models to categorize either examinees (Cohen & Bolt, 2005; Scarpati, Wells, Lewis, & Jirka, 2011) or items (Frederickx, Tuerlinckx, De Boeck, & Magis, 2010;

Soares, Goncalves, & Gamerman, 2009) as being affected by DIF. These analyses typically rely on Bayesian methods for parameter estimation and inferences because the likelihood surface may be multimodal and complex. Deriving maximum likelihood algorithms is challenging, and in some cases, impossible. Because of advancements in modern computers and the popularization of Markov chain Monte Carlo software (e.g., Winbugs; Spiegelhalter, Thomas, Best, & Lunn, 2003; JAGS; Plummer, 2003; STAN; Stan Development Team, 2014), the application of nontraditional models, where closed form expressions need not exist, is gaining traction among researchers. We consider these types of models as a modern take on DIF. That is, we only characterize these models as modern because of the popularity of Markov chain Monte Carlo techniques (MCMC) and computational efficiencies made possible through advancements in technology. The spirit behind these approaches have existed for over half a century (e.g., Green, 1952; McHugh, 1956).

The current paper examines the similarities and differences between traditional and modern methods of investigating DIF. We additionally compare them to an alternative classical Bayesian approach to model comparison, the Bayes Factor (BF). The latter method allows researchers to quantify evidence for DIF-free items; it can provide evidence for the null.

DIF: Traditional methods

Of the many types of analyses for discovering DIF items, each falls into one of several classes (for a review, see Holland & Wainer, 1993). The current study focuses on comparing traditional approaches to Bayesian ones. Perhaps the most common method of detecting DIF is the Mantel-Haenszel (MH) procedure (Holland & Thayer, 1988). This approach tests whether a relationship exists between two categorical variables after stratifying on a covariate. Items demonstrate DIF when the odds of answering an item correctly differs between the categorical variables (i.e., groups). One strength of MH is that it does not rely on an item response model and therefore makes the least amount of assumptions.

Relying on a model comparison framework, a likelihood ratio test (LRT) of nested models is another common traditional approach to modeling DIF. Thissen, Stienber, & Gerrard (1986) recommended the method of comparing a full model accounting for group effects to a null model collapsing across groups. This is carried out by taking the difference of the likelihood deviance G ($= -2 \times \log$ -likelihood; Neyman & Pearson, 1928) of the maximum likelihood estimates. In the standard method, each item is investigated for DIF individually and therefore the LRT procedure consists of many different model comparisons. The likelihood ratio test is also a popular analysis

used for testing fixed and random effects in many psychological experiments. Because an IRT model is nothing more than a generalized linear mixed model (GLMM; see Kamata, 2001; De Boeck & Wilson, 2004) and because testing for DIF is nothing more than testing a fixed effect (but see Verhagan & Fox, 2013 for a random effect formulation), many experimental psychologists are familiar with the conceptualization and application of LRTs. Therefore, one advantage of the LRT is its wide application and familiarity among many types of researchers—both those in assessment (i.e., large sample exams) and those involved in experimentation.

Despite their wide usage, both MH and LRT approaches have the draw back that they must rely on a set of anchor items, items known to be DIF-free. When no such items are known to exist a priori, researchers must use an all-other anchor set, where every item other than the one investigated is considered DIF-free. A *purification process* iteratively removes all DIF items until a final set of DIF-free items are retained. This approach is quite time consuming for the LRT method but manageable for the MH analysis. One could use the MH for determining a set of anchor items and then apply LRTs to the remaining items. However, when a large portion of the test items contain DIF items, neither method, combined nor otherwise, work well (Fidalgo, Mellenbergh, & Muniz, 2000; Wang & Yeh, 2003).

Unfortunately, in real situations it is unknown how many actual items are indeed DIF-free. Furthermore, one particular situation becoming more popular among testing programs is likely to have a higher number of DIF items. Specifically, the emergent trend of programs expanding test designs to include technology-enhanced items brings about a scenario where differential exposures to said technology produces unintended consequences in measurement. Prudently, programs carryout moderate scale studies to determine item performance across a representative sample. This sample includes both those who are and are not trained/exposed to the new technology. Examining DIF based on this classification can yield a higher than normal percentage of DIF items. In this case, maintaining a set of DIF-free anchor items is essential. When this is not possible, researchers and test developers can use an alternative Bayesian approach that avoids the iterative search-and-remove technique.

DIF: Bayesian methods

The advent of powerful computers and the popularity of MCMC resulted in more researchers adopting Bayesian methods for both parameter estimation and building sophisticated models. Bayesian parameter estimation in psychometrics has been quite popular because of the multimodal and complex likelihood surface of popular IRT models (cf. Thissen & Steinberg, 1984, who foreshadowed the popularity of Bayesian methods). However, other

areas of measurement, such as experimental psychology, have only recently promoted the use of Bayesian statistics (e.g., Mulder, Klugkist, van de Schoot, Selfhout, Hoijtink, 2009; Wagenmakers, 2007; Morey, Rouder, Verhagen, & Wagenmakers, 2014) but adoption is slow.

When sample size constraints are not an issue, as in moderate sized testing programs, the application of more sophisticated models is possible. One particular model type that addresses issues tied to anchor items is an item mixture model. Soares et al. (2009) call models of this ilk a fully integrated Bayesian model for DIF (or FIB for short). The general idea behind these models is that they treat each item as having an explicit probability of being a DIF item. Each item is therefore tested simultaneously. Frederickx et al. (2010) parametrized a Rasch IRT model with crossed-random effects, treating both candidate abilities and item difficulties as samples from a population. Abilities and item difficulties for the reference group were estimated per usual but when a latent indicator identified an item as having DIF for the focal group, a separate item difficulty was estimated. Let C_j be defined as

$$C_j = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{item } j \text{ is DIF-free,} \\ 1 & \text{item } j \text{ shows DIF,} \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

with a Bernoulli probability and the probability of responding correctly to item j given a group g defined as

$$\begin{aligned} P(y_{ijg} = 1 | C_j = 0) &= \text{logit}^{-1}(\theta_{ig} - \beta_j), \\ P(y_{ijg} = 1 | C_j = 1) &= \text{logit}^{-1}(\theta_{ig} - \beta_{jg}). \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

In the simple case of two groups, Frederickx et al. (2010) set the population distributions as

$$\begin{aligned} \theta_{i1} &\sim N(0, \sigma_{\theta_1}^2), \\ \theta_{i2} &\sim N(\mu_{\theta_2}, \sigma_{\theta_2}^2), \\ \beta_j | C_j = 0 &\sim N(\mu_{\beta}, \sigma_{\beta}^2) \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

and

$$\begin{pmatrix} \beta_{j1} \\ \beta_{j2} \end{pmatrix} | C_j = 1 \sim N \left[\begin{pmatrix} \mu_{\beta} \\ \mu_{\beta} \end{pmatrix}, \begin{pmatrix} \sigma_{\beta 1}^2 & \sigma_{\beta 1 \beta 2} \\ \sigma_{\beta 1 \beta 2} & \sigma_{\beta 2}^2 \end{pmatrix} \right]. \quad (4)$$

Notice the mean item difficulties in Equation 4 are the same for both groups. This is because items are random samples from a single population. For that reason, the authors appropriately call the model a random item mixture model (RIM). We use this parameterization as our FIB model for investigation throughout this paper.

The FIB approach to detecting DIF has several advantages over traditional ones. Most importantly, it is simultaneously a measurement and an explanatory model. First, as a measurement model, candidate abilities are no longer confounded by the presence of DIF. By obtaining separate item difficulties for each group, abilities are more accurately estimated. Of course, the careful reader understands this property only holds to the extent that the model sufficiently and reliably detects DIF. And second, as an explanatory model, FIBs are extendable to include additional covariates that explain DIF (cf. Soares et al., 2009). This makes it useful when exploring, for example, new technology-enhanced items or new methods of assessment (e.g., virtual reality, Veling, Moritz & van der Gaag, 2014). An additional strength of FIB models is that they do not require item purification to determine a set of anchor items. We investigate this property in Simulation 2.

An alternative approach to model-criticism under the Bayesian framework is the classical Bayes Factor (BF; Jeffreys, 1961; Kass & Raftery, 1995). This relies on model comparison like the LRT and is gaining traction in psychological experimentation (e.g., Rouder, Speckman, Sun, Morey, & Iverson, 2009; Dienes, 2011; Kruschke, 2011; Wetzels, Matzke, Lee, Rouder, Iverson, & Wagenmakers, 2011), where experimental designs and sample sizes are much smaller than in applied psychometrics. Sample size constraints prevent the application of more sophisticated models in basic psychological research (but see Lee, 2008 & 2011 for informative examples in cognitive modeling, a field that often uses stochastic models). Determining the viability of using BFs for investigating DIF is the key objective in this paper. But before demonstrating an application in psychometrics, we explain several key motivating factors through examples in the general linear model.

A BF quantifies the relative amount of evidence provided by the data for two (or more) competing models and is typically expressed as the ratio of two normalized constants. This latter fact distinguishes between MCMC methods for parameter estimation (e.g., FIB) and MCMC methods for calculating BFs (e.g., transdimensional MCMC; Carlin & Chib, 1995). When comparing two models \mathcal{M}_0 and \mathcal{M}_1 , the BF, \mathcal{B}_{01} is given by

$$\mathcal{B}_{01} = \frac{\int_{\theta \in \Theta_0} \Pr(\text{Data} | \mathcal{M}_0, \theta) \pi_0(\theta) d\theta}{\int_{\theta \in \Theta_1} \Pr(\text{Data} | \mathcal{M}_1, \theta) \pi_1(\theta) d\theta}, \quad (5)$$

where Θ_0 and Θ_1 are the parameter spaces for their respective models, and π_0 and π_1 are the prior probability density functions of the parameters for their respective models. Because a prior probability is required to calculate a BF, its choice receives much controversy. Priors can be categorized as subjective or objective, though the label of the latter class is somewhat deceiving as it still remains, in part, subjective. A subjective prior reflects a researcher's

a priori belief about the parameters, whereas an objective prior makes as few assumptions as possible and is determined by its theoretical properties. A prior that results in a BF that is scale invariant, consistent, and consistent in information is classified as an objective prior. The first property is accomplished by standardization. The second property is accomplished when a BF approaches the appropriate bound in the large-sample limit; if \mathcal{M}_0 holds, then the $\mathcal{B}_{01} \rightarrow \infty$, and conversely if \mathcal{M}_1 holds, $\mathcal{B}_{01} \rightarrow 0$. And the third property is accomplished when an increase in a test statistic explaining variation is concomitant with the BF. For example, if the test statistic is the coefficient of determination (R^2), the BF should indefinitely prefer the alternative model as R^2 approaches 1.

For the general linear model (i.e., regression and ANOVA), Rouder and colleagues promote the use of an objective prior that was first presented by Zellner and Siow (1980) and is briefly highlighted here. Using the recommendation of Jefferys (1961), differences are reparameterized in terms of effect size. This accomplishes the first property of standardization because effect size is $\delta = \mu/\sigma$ in the case of a normally distributed variable, e.g.,

$$y_i \sim N(\sigma\delta, \sigma^2). \quad (6)$$

Unfortunately, the properties of consistency do not hold with a normally distributed prior (see Liang, Paulo, Molina, Clyde, & Berger, 2008). Instead Zellner and Siow (1980) determined that a fat-tailed distribution, one with slowly-diminishing tails, is required to satisfy consistency. They concluded that the simplest solution is to generate a mixture of normals by placing a prior on the variance. The result is known as Zellner's g-prior, and for the slope θ is

$$\theta|g \sim N(\mathbf{0}, g(\mathbf{X}'\mathbf{X}/N)^{-1}), g \sim \text{Inverse Gamma}(1/2, s^2/2). \quad (7)$$

The common formulation of the g-prior additionally standardizes the independent variables with the scaling matrix $\mathbf{X}'\mathbf{X}/N$. Rouder et al. (2009) note that this standardization makes sense for continuous covariates but is not sensible for categorical variables (e.g., ANOVA type models) because it results in a singular matrix and requires a generalized inverse. Categorical variables, of course, is of primary interest when investigating DIF (i.e., group membership), and for that reason we rely on the Rouder et al. parameterization in this paper. The resulting marginal distribution on the slope θ is a Cauchy distribution with scale s . The properties of consistency hold using this prior in the general linear model. Despite the advantages of a Cauchy prior, regression coefficients are not often modeled this way. Liang et al. (2008) speculate this is because Cauchy priors do not permit closed form expressions of marginal likelihoods. Fortunately, stochastic algorithms allow straightforward sampling of the marginals and full posterior.

In their paper, Rouder et al. (2009) demonstrated the usefulness of the BF in experimental psychology and highlighted several benefits. The following two are the primary motivators for the research herein. First and foremost, BFs allow researchers to state evidence for the null. We evaluate the practicality of stating evidence for DIF in this manner by conducting two power simulations—one for detecting DIF items (B_{10}) and one for detecting DIF-free items (B_{01}). And second, the BF is more conservative compared to null hypothesis significance testing and requires greater amount of evidence to indicate meaningful differences. That is, conventional tests favor the alternative hypothesis relative to the null. If the BF for a generalized linear mixed model is like the BF in the general linear model, then it is reasonable to suspect similar conservative behavior. This is a desirable property when Type I error inflations are likely to occur, for example, when anchor items are contaminated with DIF (Wang & Yeh, 2003). Simulation 2 focuses on this aspect of the BF.

Calculating BFs for the likelihood of DIF requires a null and full model, as well as anchor items—just as the LRT. However, we can apply the simplification of the Savage-Dickey density ratio (Dickey & Lientz, 1970) because of the simplicity of these models and because they are nested. This allows calculating BFs from the saturated model by taking the ratio of the prior and posterior density heights at a value of interest. The comparison of the prior and posterior densities at zero corresponds to a point-null test and measures the change in likelihood for DIF. Anchors in the saturated model have equal difficulty across groups and the item under investigation has an additional item-by-group contrast coefficient. Using contrasts (i.e., sum-to-zero design matrix) rather than group indicators (i.e., treatment design matrix) has a key benefit. In contrast coding, the intercept of the item under inspection represents the overall item difficulty, it can be modeled with a vague and diffused prior. Then, a constrained prior isolates the effect of DIF separate and apart from the grand mean. For example, let β indicate the item inspected for DIF. Its intercept (α) represents the overall difficulty in the overall population. The DIF effect (δ) represents the magnitude of DIF and is modeled with a constrained prior.

$$\begin{aligned}
 \beta &= \alpha + \delta X \\
 \alpha &\sim N(0,100) \\
 \delta &\sim N(0,1) \\
 X &= \begin{cases} -.5 & \text{reference group,} \\ .5 & \text{focal group.} \end{cases}
 \end{aligned} \tag{8}$$

Conversely, using group indicators requires one to place a diffused prior on the reference group but a constrained prior on the focal group. Such that the indicator variable X is

$$X = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{reference group,} \\ 1 & \text{focal group,} \end{cases}$$

with α representing the item difficulty in the reference group and δ representing the effect for the focal group. This is an unsatisfactory parameterization because of the arbitrary choice in modeling one group as more diffused than another group. It is especially problematic with unbalanced groups.

Separate models are constructed for each inspected item, and thus, the BF model comparison is just like the model comparison for the LRT method. At this point it is important to note other similarities between the BF and LRT. Both methods can be viewed as ratios of the likelihood of the observed (variation in the) data of two competing hypotheses (models). However, the LRT *maximizes* over the parameter space whereas the BF *integrates* over the parameter space (Kass & Raftery, 1995). The LRT relies on asymptotic distributional assumptions to draw inferences, whereas the BF simply states the relative evidence between the compared models. For valid inferences, the LRT must assume the null model is true and therefore only inspects evidence for the alternative. Despite the controversy caused by that assumption, the LRT is quite powerful at testing exact (i.e., simple) hypotheses.

By integrating over the parameter space, the BF approach allows inclusion of additional information. So, for example, analysts can specify probable values on the expected effect of DIF in a data set. A prior with most of its mass on zero indicates the belief that items are mostly DIF-free. By contrast, diffusing the prior increases the a priori belief that DIF is present and can take on large values. Because the BF quantifies the change in beliefs after observing data, specification of prior beliefs is quite important. In the end, the LRT and the BF are closely related, but the BF has more natural flexibility (although generalizations of the LRT exist). This flexibility is partly attributed to the influence of the priors, and for this reason, sensible priors are essential for sensible BFs.

An objective prior on the effect of DIF is challenging to obtain, so in Simulation 1 we chose to model 3 variations. Satisfying scale invariance is straightforward. Dividing coefficients by the residual standard deviation standardizes them in the general linear model. No such division is required in the GLMM because the coefficients are already standardized to the population standard deviation of the random effect (e.g., the ability distribution in IRT models). Steinberg and Thissen (2006) made this argument when they addressed a growing desire to report effect sizes in empirical studies. Using DIF as an example, they reasoned that reporting the difference in the item difficulty parameter between groups is a sufficient effect size measure. It is comparable across studies when the

population standard deviation is known (or estimated). Thus, by fixing the population or a subset of the population (i.e., one group for model identifiability) to a unit-normal, differences in parameters are comparable across different studies. By extension of this argument, scale invariance is met and we can put a sensible prior on the effect size of DIF and use that prior to calculate BFs.

We cannot help but wonder whether the properties of consistency extend to the GLMM. Sabanes Bove and Held (2011) generalized the g-prior for linked linear models but stopped short of reporting whether consistency holds. Instead, the authors suggested that the property may hold but will likely remain unknown because fewer closed form expressions are available, and thus, derivations of proofs continue to challenge researchers. Furthermore, we can think of no *perfect* expression to explain variation in GLMMs. Each statistic suffers from at least one undesirable property (e.g., cannot perfectly approach 1 when all the variation is explained; see Nakagawa & Schielzeth, 2013). This led us to examine differences between three different priors in Simulation 1; the unit-normal, unit-Cauchy, and half-unit-Cauchy priors. We make no claim that these priors are objective but instead consider them as sensibly subjective.

We compare the detectability of DIF between the Mantel-Haenszel, likelihood ratio test, fully integrated Bayesian, and Bayes Factors approach in the following two simulations. Specifically, we are interested in the power to detect DIF and the Type I false alarms. We first inspect the properties of the BF and under ideal conditions and compare it to the other DIF methods in Simulation 1. This is accomplished by varying the number of anchor items that are truly DIF-free. Then we inspect the properties of the BF when anchor items are misspecified in Simulation 2. This is accomplished by using the all-other anchor method. Much research has demonstrated the impact of using known anchor items when conducting LRT or MH analyses. The all-other anchor method results in reduced power and increased Type 1 errors when a test contains higher levels of DIF items. We see whether the conservative nature of the BF can offset any potential Type 1 error rate inflations in Simulation 2.

Simulation 1

Simulation 1 employed a two group balanced DIF design; half of the simulated examinees had reference group membership and the remaining half had focal group membership. The abilities of the reference group, focal group, and item difficulties were drawn from a standard normal distribution. We factorially manipulated the following variables for a 20-item exam with 5 DIF items:

1. the number of anchor items (1, 5, 10);

2. the DIF size (.4, .6, .8); and
3. the sample size (500, 1000).

Items designated as DIF were more difficult for the focal group by the DIF size factor (e.g., .4, .6, or .8 logits were added to item difficulties for the focal group). Each cell in the fully crossed design was replicated 100 times.

We used Frederickx et al.'s (2010) parameterization and their default priors as our FIB model (the population distributions are described above and the remaining priors are found in the authors' paper). The DIF indicator variable (C_j) was set a priori for the anchor items so that they were designated as DIF-free items and had equal difficulty estimates across the two groups. We used JAGS to sample the posterior distribution and ran four chains of 10,000 iterations, with 3,000 iterations for tuning the sampler, and the 3,500 iterations that followed were treated as burn-ins. In addition to randomly examining parameter trace plots, we assessed convergence with the \hat{R} criterion (Brooks & Gelman, 1998) and roughly 96% of all the estimated parameters had values less than 1.1, indicating the chains converged. In accordance with previous studies, we determined items as having DIF by examining the MCMC output for the DIF indicator variable (C_j), which approximates the posterior probability of DIF for item j . That is, an item is said to have DIF when $C_j = 1$ for more than half of the retained samples.

We estimated the BF model in a similar fashion, but used STAN as our sampler because it was more efficient sampling the parameter space. STAN uses the No-U-Turn algorithm to optimize a Hamiltonian Monte Carlo (HMC) sampler adaptively. This works exceptionally well for the BF model but does not work for the FIB model because, unfortunately, STAN's HMC implementation cannot sample discrete latent distributions (i.e., discrete parameters). Using STAN, we ran the same number of chains, tuning iterations, and burn-in samples as mentioned above. We ran separate models to inspect each non-anchor item for DIF: 19 models in the 1-anchor condition, 15 models in the 5-anchor condition, and 10 models in the 10-anchor condition. We placed uninformed priors on item difficulties, including the intercept of the item under inspection, and on the ability difference between the two groups. The latter was done because the primary interest is not measuring the difference between abilities of the groups, per se. Furthermore, the effect is equivalent between the null and saturated models and therefore integrated out.

A unit-normal, unit-Cauchy, and half-unit-Cauchy prior expressed three different a priori beliefs about the DIF effect. The unit-Cauchy has fatter tails than the unit-normal and expresses the a priori belief that DIF is more

likely in the data (with the half-unit-Cauchy expressing even more belief). As mentioned above, the BF quantifies the likelihood of DIF (or lack thereof) *relative* to the a priori belief of DIF. The unit-Cauchy, then, requires more evidence from the data to suggest that any particular item is a DIF item. Conversely, the unit-normal has more mass at zero than the unit-Cauchy, which could pull (shrink) the estimate of DIF closer to zero. As a consequence, it requires less evidence in the data to favor DIF. These counteracting forces serve as additional motivation to inspect the behavior of the unit-normal, unit-Cauchy, and half-unit-Cauchy priors on the DIF effect.

Despite these differences in the priors, we still expect the BF to yield conservative behavior compared to the LRT approach. Bayes Factors were calculated using the Savage-Dickey density ratio (Dickey & Lientz, 1970) from the MCMC output and were analyzed on two aspects. The first was evidence favoring DIF, and items were identified as DIF items when $B_{10} > 3$ (i.e., favoring the DIF hypothesis three times over the null). The second was evidence favoring an item as DIF-free, and items were identified as DIF-free when $B_{01} > 3$ (i.e., favoring the null hypothesis three times over the alternative). This makes it clear that there might not be enough evidence in the data to classify some items as either DIF or DIF-free. We find this transparency a desirable property of the BF and report power for both types of analyses. However, we only compare the BF for evidence favoring DIF to the other DIF methods because the LRT and MH only state evidence for the alternative hypothesis.

To conduct the LRT analyses, the Rasch model was parameterized as a GLMM (see Doran, Bates, Bliese, & Dowling, 2007; De Boeck et al., 2011) and the lme4 package for R estimated the maximum likelihood of the parameters (Bates, Maechler, Bolker, & Walker, 2014; R Development Core Team, 2008). A full and nested model controlled for differences in ability between the groups and the full model tested for the item-by-group interaction (i.e., DIF). This was done separately for each item. The alpha level was set at the conventional 0.05 for all tests. We used the difR package (Magis, Beland, Raiche, 2013) for the MH procedure and set the same conventional alpha level.

Results

Simulation 1 results are presented in the following order. First, we compare the B_{10} across the three priors. Then we compare that BF to the remaining DIF detection methods. And finally, we compare the B_{01} across the three priors and demonstrate the power of detecting DIF-free items under the simulated factors.

The proportion of correctly identified DIF items using the BF method and one, five, and ten anchor items is displayed in Figure 1, 2, and 3, respectively. There are four apparent general trends. Detectability of DIF increases

as 1) the DIF effect increases, 2) the sample size increases, and 3) the number of anchor items increases. These three findings are not that surprising and consistent with other findings using related DIF methods (see Wang & Yeh, 2003). The final pattern in the data is that the unit-normal prior and the half-unit-Cauchy has equivalent power in detecting DIF items, and the unit-Cauchy has slightly less power at detecting modest sized DIF effects. However, these differences mitigate at higher levels of DIF and when using more anchor items.

Figure 1. The percentage of correctly identified DIF items using one anchor item as a function of sample size, DIF size, and prior on DIF.

Figure 2. The percentage of correctly identified DIF items using five anchor items as a function of sample size, DIF size, and prior on DIF.

Figure 3. The percentage of correctly identified DIF items using ten anchor items as a function of sample size, DIF size, and prior on DIF.

No systematic pattern appears across the three different priors for Type I errors. This is because the error rate is very low. In general, errors are reduced with more anchor items and when increasing sample size. No other clear pattern emerged. All levels are well below what has been reported for the MH and LRT methods. Figures 4, 5, and 6 display the results when using one, five, and ten anchor items, respectively.

Figure 4. The percentage of Type I errors for missidentified DIF-Free items using one anchor item as a function of sample size, DIF size, and prior on DIF.

Figure 5. The percentage of Type I errors for missidentified DIF-Free items using five anchor items as a function of sample size, DIF size, and prior on DIF.

Figure 6. The percentage of Type I errors for missidentified DIF-Free items using ten anchor items as a function of sample size, DIF size, and prior on DIF.

In summary, the three different priors identified DIF at roughly equivalent rates and had similar Type I errors. They are all conservative compared to conventional tests. That is, the B_{10} , evidence for DIF, seems to not favor the alternative hypothesis as much as would be expected from conventional tests using a .05 nominal alpha. We look at this more directly in a following section and now turn to comparing the B_{10} to the other DIF methods of interest.

Figures 7 through 9 plot the power for detecting DIF in the order of increasing anchors. The unit-normal prior is used as a reference point to draw comparisons between the BF and the other methods. The results are characterized by the following patterns. First, DIF is detected at higher rates with larger DIF effects between the reference and focal group. Second, detection rates increase steadily with more anchor items, but the combination of anchor items and DIF size result in ceiling performance. Third, the FIB method is under powered in detecting small DIF effects relative to the other methods. This difference mitigates with DIF of 0.6 logits or greater and when using more anchor items, although the FIB still has slightly less power with five or more anchor items. The difference is quite small but systematic nevertheless. And finally, across all factors, the BF is slightly more conservative, and therefore has slightly less powerful, than the LRT. This finding corresponds to what has been reported in the general linear model (see Rouder et al., 2009).

Figure 7. The percentage of correctly identified DIF items using one anchor item as a function of sample size, DIF size, and DIF detection method. The red lines correspond to the values obtained with the unit-normal BF.

Figure 8. The percentage of correctly identified DIF items using five anchor items as a function of sample size, DIF size, and DIF detection method. The red lines correspond to the values obtained with the unit-normal BF.

Figure 9. The percentage of correctly identified DIF items using ten anchor items as a function of sample size, DIF size, and DIF detection method. The red lines correspond to the values obtained with the unit-normal BF.

The following set of figures show the Type I error rates for the unit-normal BF, FIB, LRT, and MH. The LRT and MH methods hold their nominal alpha level with either one anchor item (Figure 10), five anchor items (Figure 11), or ten anchor items (Figure 12). The BF results in fewer false positives, further establishing its conservative nature. One interesting pattern to note is the error rate inflation that occurs with the FIB method when using ten anchor items. This is attributed to the nature of latently classifying items when a high proportion of items contain DIF. With ten anchor items, half of the remaining items are DIF items. Error rate inflation is further investigated in Simulation 2.

Figure 10. The percentage of Type I errors for misidentified DIF-Free items using one anchor item as a function of sample size, DIF size, DIF detection method. The red lines correspond to the values obtained with the unit-normal BF.

Figure 11. The percentage of Type I errors for misidentified DIF-Free items using five anchor items as a function of sample size, DIF size, DIF detection method. The red lines correspond to the values obtained with the unit-normal BF.

Figure 12. The percentage of Type I errors for misidentified DIF-Free items using ten anchor items as a function of sample size, DIF size, DIF detection method. The red lines correspond to the values obtained with the unit-normal BF.

As repeatedly shown, the B_{10} is a conservative statistic. It has fewer false positives and slightly less power than the LRT. To further inspect the difference between these two approaches, we carried out the LRT method to each of the three sets of data used for the BF (i.e., the 100 replications for each of the priors; the unit-normal, the unit-Cauchy, and the half-unit-Cauchy). Then we transformed the BF to the deviance scale—the scale that the likelihood ratio statistic is on (twice the natural logarithm of the BF; Kass & Raftery, 1995). Figure 13 displays these values and clearly shows that, relative to the BF, the LRT favors the alternative hypothesis—it overstates the evidence for DIF.

Figure 13. Evidence in favor of the alternative hypothesis (i.e., DIF) of the BF and likelihood ratio test. The BF for the half-unit-Cauchy, unit-Cauchy, and unit-normal are converted to the deviance scale of the likelihood ratio. The lower right hand of each panel displays the slope of the best fitting linear function.

Lastly, we analyze the power and error rates of using the B_{01} , the evidence in favor of the null. Items are classified as DIF-free when the null is favored three-to-one over the alternative. The LRT and MH cannot evaluate evidence for the null and therefore drawing comparisons to those methods is nonsensical. The FIB method can approximate the evidence for or against DIF by analyzing the mixing proportions of the latent class (in this case, inspecting the proportion of the DIF indicator variable in favor of the null from the MCMC output). However, this is not directly comparable to the BFs reported herein because the FIB approach indicates the likelihood of DIF for

each item given the likelihood of DIF in each of the remaining items (i.e., a top-down approach). By contrast, the BF we present takes a bottom-up approach and models the likelihood of DIF for each item separately (i.e., an intercept only null model, with the intercept being the overall item difficulty value). For these reasons, we do not compare the B_{01} to the other DIF methods and instead focus on differences between the three BF priors.

The percentage of correctly identified DIF-free items for one anchor item, five anchor items, and ten anchor items are displayed in Figure 14, 15, and 16, respectively. The half-unit-Cauchy is too diffused to detect any substantial amount of DIF-free items with one anchor item ($< 1\%$). By contrast, one anchor item is sufficient for correctly identifying roughly 80% of DIF-free items using the unit-Cauchy prior. Unfortunately, there is little added value to using more anchor items. The remaining trends in these data are such that 1) the unit-Cauchy is more powerful than the unit-normal, 2) increasing sample size increases the power to detect DIF-free items, and 3) the DIF size for the remaining items has no bearing on detecting DIF-free items (as expected because that variable pertains to a different class of items). Although power approaches or exceeds a respectable value of 80% (detectability percentage), they asymptote quickly and never exceed values of 90%. One reason behind this result is that it is increasingly difficult to provide evidence for a point-null hypothesis. That is, providing evidence that the difference in item difficulties between the reference and focal group is *exactly* zero. We revisit this topic briefly in the concluding statements.

Figure 14. The percentage of correctly identified DIF-free items using one anchor item as a function of sample size, DIF size, and prior on DIF.

Figure 15. The percentage of correctly identified DIF-free items using five anchor items as a function of sample size, DIF size, and prior on DIF.

Figure 16. The percentage of correctly identified DIF-free items using ten anchor items as a function of sample size, DIF size, and prior on DIF.

We inspect Type I errors of misclassifying DIF items as DIF-free in the next set of figures. First, regardless of the number of anchor items, a high proportion of DIF items are misclassified as DIF-free when the effect is small and when using either a unit-Cauchy or unit-normal prior. Even with the increased sample size of 1,000 examinees, the Type 1 error is high. If consistency holds for the unit-Cauchy prior, the rate that the BF approaches the correct bound is too slow for small DIF effects. However, these error rates must be considered in relation to the Type II error rates of LRT method, which have a similar interpretation (i.e., classifying DIF items as DIF-free). In all cases, the BF for the null outperforms the LRT. As seen in Figure 17, the half-unit-Cauchy does not produce many Type I errors, but this is because it cannot adequately detect items as DIF-free (see Figure 14 where the half-unit-Cauchy is severely underpowered). For effects larger than 0.4 logits, increasing the number of anchor items produces fewer misclassifications of DIF items (see Figures 18 and 19). With 1,000 examinees, Type I errors are substantially reduced.

Figure 17. The percentage of Type I errors for missidentified DIF items using one anchor item as a function of sample size, DIF size, and prior on DIF.

Figure 18. The percentage of Type I errors for missidentified DIF items using five anchor items as a function of sample size, DIF size, and prior on DIF.

Figure 19. The percentage of Type I errors for missidentified DIF items using ten anchor items as a function of sample size, DIF size, and prior on DIF.

The results from Simulation 1 are summarized as follows. First, the BF yields similar performance to that of the LRT when providing evidence for DIF. However, it is more conservative than the LRT. This is shown by comparing the evidence favoring DIF between the LRT and the BF. Second, the FIB works well for modest sized DIF effects but produces higher Type I errors when a higher proportion of DIF items are present in an exam. Third, increasing anchor items improves DIF detectability (but see Figure 12). This is the case for all methods except for the B_{01} where power asymptotes quickly. And fourth, the B_{01} seems suitable for expressing evidence favoring the null, with power reaching 80% detectability in nearly all conditions. However, this results in higher than desirable misclassifications of DIF items for small effects. A modified scaled prior, perhaps with a scale of 0.75 might strike a good balance between power and Type 1 error rate. Collectively, we demonstrate 1) the potential usefulness of using the BF to detecting DIF and 2) the conservative property of the BF. The latter point is further explored in the following simulation.

Simulation 2

To explore whether the BF maintains its conservative property, we ran a follow-up simulation using the all-other anchor method. Every item other than the item under inspection is assumed to be DIF-free. No anchor items

were used in the FIB analysis and all items were tested contemporaneously. We used a unit-normal prior for the BF because it struck a decent balance between power, Type 1 error rates, and computational efficiency.

The design follows closely to a scenario where a potentially high number of DIF items are present in an assessment, for example, what might be expected when piloting a virtual reality assessment to those with and without experience/exposure to the technology. Imagine placing examinees in medical virtual reality scenarios where they must interact with and diagnose patients, undergo surgical procedures, or other medically related tasks. Conceivably, examinees trained with virtual reality technology might be advantaged in a high proportion of the scenarios. Furthermore, Simulation 2 was identical to Simulation 1 save for the following changes. The factor manipulating the number of anchor items was replaced with a factor manipulating the number of DIF items. Therefore, the following factorial design was used for a 20 item exam:

1. the sample size (500, 1000);
2. the number of DIF items (5, 10); and
3. the DIF size (.4, .6, .8).

As before, we modeled two group balanced DIF design with half of the simulated examinees belonging to the reference group and the remaining half belonging to the focal group. All abilities and item difficulties were drawn from a standard normal distribution and DIF items were manipulated in a similar fashion as Simulation 1. Finally, each cell in the factorial design was replicated 40 times rather than 100. This is because both the LRT and BF methods were much more computationally intensive. No other changes were made and items were identified as having DIF using the same rules as before.

Results

Our primary interest is the relative performance of the BF because this analysis allows researchers to frame effects in terms of the null, which seems more natural for DIF investigation. Previous studies demonstrate inflations of Type I errors for the LRT when tests comprise a high percentage of DIF items (Wang & Yeh, 2003), and we anticipate a similar finding here. But it is unclear how much inflation will occur for the BF because of its conservative nature. The lack of favor for the alternative hypothesis (i.e., DIF) may yield fewer Type I errors, perhaps within reasonable levels.

The percentage of correctly identified DIF items when five of twenty items are contaminated by DIF is displayed in Figure 20 and the accompanying Type I errors are displayed in Figure 21. Frequentist power analyses

are conditional on the Type I error rate, and as shown, are substantially inflated. Accordingly, we caution interpretation of the power results. Nevertheless, the following trends were observed. First, more DIF items are detected with a larger sample size and with larger DIF effects. As in Simulation 1, the FIB is relatively underpowered for the smallest DIF level, but this mitigates quickly. The Type I errors are inflated over the nominal alpha for the MH and the LRT, which correspond with previously published results. The BF is more conservative than the LRT but this counteracting force is not sufficiently strong enough to combat the concomitant inflation that occurs with contaminated anchor items.

We only report two findings for the results when ten of the twenty items are contaminated by DIF because of the egregious Type I inflation rates. Specifically, the LRT and MH had the highest error rates across all conditions (>35% for 0.6 DIF; >45% for 0.8 DIF). The unit-normal BF had comparable error rates to FIB method, which were also inflated (~ 10% for 0.4 DIF; ~20% for 0.6 DIF; ~ 30% for 0.8 DIF). Two interesting points are worth mentioning. One, the BF continues to demonstrate its conservative nature relative to the LRT, even in extreme cases. And two, the BF error rates are just as inflated as the FIB method, which performs very well when only five items are contaminated by DIF.

The findings in Simulation 2 lead us to recommend the use of known anchor items when applying the BF method to discovering and reporting DIF. The unit-normal prior is not conservative enough to prevent inflations in Type I errors when anchor items are contaminated by DIF. The upper bound in error rates is unacceptably high and necessitates the use of known anchor items.

Figure 20. The percentage of correctly identified DIF items using the all-other anchor method and with 5 DIF items.

The prior for the BF is a unit-normal.

Figure 21. The percentage of Type I errors for misidentified DIF-free items using all-other anchor method and with 5 DIF items. The prior for the BF is a unit-normal.

Conclusion

We conclude this paper by first summarizing the main findings in the presented simulations and then offer several suggestions for the practical application of the BF.

Simulation 1 involved manipulations of the sample size, DIF size, and number of anchor items. Power in detecting DIF increased with a larger sample size and with larger DIF. The FIB method performed worst at the smallest level of DIF but had sufficient power to detect greater magnitudes of DIF. Furthermore, it outperformed all the methods when some anchor items were contaminated with DIF (Simulation 2). The LRT and MH held their nominal alpha levels across all the factors in the first simulation and maintained adequate power for detecting DIF of 0.6 logits and greater. However, the introduction of contaminated anchor items in Simulation 2 inflated the Type I error rate. The use of known *pure* anchor items is essential for applying these methods.

Three separate priors for the BF were investigated in Simulation 1. When stating evidence for the alternative (i.e., DIF), all three performed somewhat equivalently. The patterns of power and Type I error rates were similar to the LRT, but in most cases were more conservative. We demonstrated the conservative nature by comparing the evidence in favor for DIF between the BF and LRT. The LRT favored the alternative more so than either of the three priors, and even at an increasing rate. Despite this fact, the BF still suffers from Type I error inflation when anchor items are contaminated by DIF (Simulation 2). Therefore, as with the LRT and MH, it is essential to use pure anchor items with the BF method.

In addition to stating the evidence in favor of DIF, the BF can state evidence for the null, the lack of DIF. The power to detect DIF-free items reaches acceptable levels for even small effects. Furthermore, the accompanied Type I error rate, falsely classifying DIF items as DIF-free, needs to be considered in relation to the LRT Type II error rates—both errors refer to falsely classifying DIF items as DIF-free. The unit-normal BF outperforms the LRT in all cases.

One main focus of the current research was demonstrating the viability of using the BF for stating evidence for the null, much like what is becoming increasingly popular in experimental psychology. However, there are several important things to consider before placing this method in practice. The current study tested BF against a point-null hypothesis: The difference in item difficulty between the reference and focal group is *exactly* zero. This requires substantial amount of evidence to favor the null. In fact, many argue that no effect is truly zero, and instead

require some region of practical equivalence (Kruschke, 2011). An alternative method to calculating BF is using an encompassing prior (Klugkist, Kato, & Hoiijtink, 2005). Using this method, the null is an interval rather than a point.

Regardless of which method one uses for calculating BFs, they must carefully choose an appropriate prior—one that accurately expresses a priori belief about the presence of DIF. Although we simulated the relative performance between three popular choices, these priors are far from exhaustive. Therefore we recommend that those looking to pursue the BF first begin by simulating conditions relevant to their application. For example, conditions that more closely resemble test length, number of candidates per group, and number of viable anchor items. In addition, we suggest comparing several different priors, much like in Simulation 1. Because deterministic approaches only provide evidence for the alternative, and because they rely on asymptotic distributions, error rates are theoretically known and controlled through a nominal alpha level. This is not applicable to Bayesian analyses. In the end, our results are promising for the BF and are generalizable to many common DIF designs. But ironically, we suggest that the prudent analyst become Bayesian in spirit and leverage his prior knowledge to construct sensible priors in order to obtain sensible BFs.

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